

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Figure S1: Depth-resolved vertical profiles of bioclimatic temperature variables. Basin-averaged vertical profiles of nine temperature-based bioclimatic variables under present (2006-2030; blue) and future (2031-2055; red) conditions are shown across the four depth zones of the Mediterranean Sea (euphotic, mesophotic, mesopelagic, bathyabysopelagic).

Figure S1 (continued)

Figure S2: Depth-specific correlations among changes in bioclimatic variables. Heatmaps show pairwise correlations among spatial changes ($\Delta = \text{future} - \text{present}$) in nine temperature-based bioclimatic variables, calculated separately for four Mediterranean depth zones (euphotic, mesophotic, mesopelagic, and bathyabysopelagic). Colour intensity indicates the sign and magnitude of correlations, using a shared colour scale across all panels.

Figure S3: Interpretation of the principal component analysis (PCA) of bioclimatic variables.

(a) Cumulative explained variance and scree plot for the PCA performed on nine standardised temperature-based bioclimatic variables. Dashed horizontal lines indicate cumulative variance thresholds of 95% (green) and 99% (red).

(b) Heatmaps showing correlations between standardised bioclimatic variables and scores of the first three principal components (PC1-PC3), calculated separately for the four Mediterranean depth zones (euphotic, mesophotic, mesopelagic, bathyabyssopelagic). Colours represent the sign and magnitude of correlations (from -1 in blue to 1 in red).

Figure S4: Sensitivity analysis of climate velocity thresholds used to define climatic analogues. Results are shown separately for each depth range (euphotic, mesophotic, mesopelagic, bathyabysopelagic). For each depth range, two panels are presented: (i) the median distance to the selected climate analogue and (ii) the proportion of the domain classified as no analogue. In panel (i), the shaded grey area indicates the interquartile range (25-75%).

Figure S5: Mediterranean basin delineation used in the study. Map of the Mediterranean Sea showing basin boundaries following the regional subdivision proposed by Manca et al. (2004). Latitude and longitude are shown in decimal degrees using the WGS 84 geographic coordinate system (EPSG:4326).

Figure S6: Surface and bottom-restricted climate velocity patterns across the Mediterranean Sea.

(a) Climate velocity at the surface layer (0.5 m), showing mean horizontal velocity (left) and mean vertical velocity (right). Horizontal velocity is displayed using a sequential colour scale from grey (null velocity) to yellow–blue (increasing velocity magnitude), while vertical velocity is shown using a diverging colour scale from negative values (blue; downward shifts) to positive values (red; upward shifts), with grey indicating null vertical movement. Purple points denote locations without a valid climatic analogue.

(b) Mean climate velocity calculated by restricting the analogue searches to bottom grid cells. Colours follow the same scale used for horizontal velocity, as the resulting velocity represents a two-dimensional (horizontal) climate velocity.

Figure S7: Summary of depth-resolved climate velocity patterns in the Adriatic basin. Panels show: (a) horizontal and vertical components of climate velocity displayed separately for each depth zone; (b) depth-wise proportions of locations exhibiting null climate velocity and no analogue conditions; (c) mean vertical displacement of climate analogues for each depth layer; (d) directional distribution (rose diagrams) of horizontal climate-driven movement for each depth zone. Climate velocity metrics are derived from analogue-based calculations performed across the full Mediterranean domain.

Figure S8: Summary of depth-resolved climate velocity patterns in the Aegean basin, shown using the same layout and metrics as Figure S7.

Figure S9: Summary of depth-resolved climate velocity patterns in the Alboran-Algerian basin, shown using the same layout and metrics as Figure S7.

Figure S10: Summary of depth-resolved climate velocity patterns in the Ionian basin, shown using the same layout and metrics as Figure S7.

Figure S11: Summary of depth-resolved climate velocity patterns in the Levantine basin, shown using the same layout and metrics as Figure S7.

Figure S12: Summary of depth-resolved climate velocity patterns in the Provencal basin, shown using the same layout and metrics as Figure S7.

Figure S13: Summary of depth-resolved climate velocity patterns in the Sicily Strait basin, shown using the same layout and metrics as Figure S7.

Figure S14: Summary of depth-resolved climate velocity patterns in the Tyrrhenian basin, shown using the same layout and metrics as Figure S7.

Table S1: Vertical biozones and depth stratification used in the analysis. For each biozone, the table reports the depth range (m), the minimum and maximum vertical spacing between adjacent depth layers, and the depth layers included.

Vertical biozones	Step between layers	Vertical layers (m)
EUPHOTIC ZONE (0-40 m)	Min 1 m Max 10 m	0.5
		1.5
		2.5
		5
		7.5
		10
		20
		30
		40
		MESOPHOTIC ZONE (40-200 m)
60		
70		
80		
90		
100		
125		
150		
175		
200		
MESOPELAGIC ZONE (200-1000 m)	Min 50 m Max 100 m	250
		300
		350
		400
		450
		500
		600
		700
		800
		900
1000		
BATHYABISSOPELAGIC ZONE (> 1000 m)	Min 250 m Max 500 m	1250
		1500
		2000
		2500
		3000
		3500
		4000
		4500
		5000
		5500

Table S2: Temperature-based bioclimatic variables used in the analysis. The table lists variable codes, full names, units, and descriptions of the climatic information represented by each variable. Definitions follow O'Donnell & Ignizio (2012).

CODE	VARIABLE NAME	DESCRIPTION
BIO1	Annual Mean Temperature	Average temperature across the year <u>Unit:</u> Degree Celsius (°C)
BIO2	Annual Mean Diurnal Range	The mean of the monthly temperature ranges (monthly maximum minus monthly minimum) <u>Unit:</u> Degree Celsius (°C)
BIO3	Isothermality	It quantifies how large the day-to-night temperatures oscillate relative to the summer-to-winter (annual) oscillations <u>Unit:</u> Percent
BIO4	Temperature Seasonality (Standard Deviation)	The amount of temperature variation over a given year (or averaged years) based on the standard deviation (variation) of monthly temperature averages <u>Unit:</u> Degree Celsius (°C)
BIO5	Max Temperature of Warmest Month	The maximum monthly temperature occurrence over a given year (time-series) or averaged span of years (normal) <u>Unit:</u> Degree Celsius (°C)
BIO6	Min Temperature of Coldest Month	The minimum monthly temperature occurrence over a given year (time series) or averaged span of years (normal) <u>Unit:</u> Degree Celsius (°C)
BIO7	Annual Temperature Range	A measure of temperature variation over a given period <u>Unit:</u> Degree Celsius (°C)
BIO10	Mean Temperature of Warmest Quarter	This quarterly index approximates mean temperatures that prevail during the warmest quarter <u>Unit:</u> Degree Celsius (°C)
BIO11	Mean Temperature of Coldest Quarter	This quarterly index approximates mean temperatures that prevail during the coldest quarter <u>Unit:</u> Degree Celsius (°C)

Table S3: Sub-basin and basin definitions used for basin-specific climate velocity analyses. The table lists Mediterranean sub-basins following the subdivision proposed by Manca et al., (2004), which were grouped to define broader basins. Sub-basin DJ was further subdivided into separate Adriatic and Ionian basins. For each sub-basin, the table reports its geographic extent (minimum and maximum latitude and longitude), the original sub-basin code and name, and the corresponding basin code and basin name used in this study.

Code Sub-basin	Sub-basin	Lat N (min)	Lat N (max)	Lon E (min)	Lon E (max)	Code basin	Basin
<i>Western Mediterranean</i>							
DF1	Algero-Provencal	39 18'	41 00'	04 30'	09 18'	DF	Provencal
DF2	Gulf of Lions	41 00'	43 36'	01 00'	06 18'		
DF3	Liguro-Provencal	41 00'	45 00'	06 18'	09 18'		
DF4	Ligurian East	42 48'	45 00'	09 18'	11 00'		
DI1	Sardinia Channel	36 00'	39 18'	08 24'	10 00'	DI	Sicily Strait
DI3	Sicily Strait	30 00'	38 00'	10 00'	15 00'		
DS1	Alboran Sea	35 00'	37 30'	-05 36'	-01 00'	DS	Alboran-Algerian
DS2	Balearic Sea	38 30'	41 00'	-01 00'	04 30'		
DS3	Algerian West	35 36'	38 30'	-01 00'	04 30'		
DS4	Algerian East	36 30'	39 18'	04 30'	08 24'		
DT1	Tyrrhenian North	38 18'	42 48'	09 18'	13 48'	DT	Tyrrhenian
DT2	Tyrrhenian East	38 18'	41 18'	13 48'	16 16'		
DT3	Tyrrhenian South	38 00'	39 18'	10 00'	16 16'		
<i>Eastern Mediterranean</i>							
DH1	Aegean North	38 00'	41 12'	22 30'	27 00'	DH	Aegean
DH2	Aegean South	35 10'	38 00'	22 30'	27 00'		
DH3	Cretan Passage	30 00'	35 10'	22 30'	27 00'		
DJ1	Adriatic North	42 00'	46 00'	12 10'	13 50'	DJa	Adriatic
DJ2	Adriatic Middle	41 18'	46 00'	13 50'	16 16'		
DJ3	Adriatic South	40 30'	44 00'	16 16'	20 00'		
DJ4	Ionian North-East	38 00'	40 30'	18 05'	22 30'	DJi	Ionian
DJ5	Ionian South	30 00'	35 10'	15 00'	22 30'		
DJ6	Ionian North-West	38 00'	40 30'	16 16'	18 05'		
DJ7	Ionian Middle West	35 10'	38 00'	15 00'	19 00'		
DJ8	Ionian Middle East	35 10'	38 00'	19 00'	22 30'		
DL1	Levantine North	33 50'	38 00'	27 00'	32 10'	DL	Levantine
DL2	Levantine North-East	34 35'	38 00'	32 10'	38 00'		
L3	Levantine South	30 00'	33 50'	27 00'	32 10'		
DL4	Levantine South-East	30 00'	34 35'	32 10'	38 00'		

REFERENCES

- Manca, B., Burca, M., Giorgetti, A., Coatanoan, C., Garcia, M.-J., & Iona, A. (2004). Physical and biochemical averaged vertical profiles in the Mediterranean regions: An important tool to trace the climatology of water masses and to validate incoming data from operational oceanography. *Journal of Marine Systems*, 48(1–4), 83–116. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmarsys.2003.11.025>
- O'Donnell, M. S., & Ignizio, D. A. (2012). *Data Series 691—Bioclimatic Predictors for Supporting Ecological Applications in the Conterminous United States* (Data Series) [Data Series]. U.S. Department of the Interior, U.S. Geological Survey.